

The influence of the travel experience of network virtual community on tourists: A life experience

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Abstract

Nowadays, with the rapid development of information technology, the tourism virtual community not only plays the role of information dissemination and exchange but also becomes a new tool for people to organize tourism activities. The characteristics of tourists and service management are the main factors that affect the perception of Wuyuan tourists in the online virtual community. Among them, pleasant natural landscapes and antique cultural landscapes are the most important influencing factors of the Wuyuan tourism experience, while other factors include season, weather, transportation, and consumption price. The Internet is a virtual space with remarkable characteristics of agglomeration and withdrawal. The interaction in the network can derive cohesive interpersonal trust through the dissemination of fragmented information. However, due to the virtual nature of the network, trust between community users is much more fragile than in offline communities, and it is also more difficult to establish. The development of the entire virtual community will be seriously constrained by the loss of trust in the network community. Therefore, it is necessary to deeply study the influencing factors of online interpersonal trust in the tourism virtual community and how to build a high-trust online community.

Keywords: *Tourism virtual community; Network interaction; Cognition; Image perception; Life experience.*

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Introduction

A virtual community is a community composed of people with common interests in a virtual environment. In a virtual community, people socialize and interact with each other, and they can also provide a platform and channel for business transactions. In the real world, they have established countless social relationships and constructed a real society through interactive communication. Similarly, communication and interaction in the Internet world have also derived a network society in a virtual context. Virtual communities are network societies one by one. The tourism virtual community came into people's eyes, broke the restriction of geographical space and other factors, and became a platform to connect the vast number of tourism enthusiasts, greatly realizing the connection of tourists.

In the past, the community formed by tourism enthusiasts was restricted by geographical and spatial factors, which were not conducive to the development of community activities. Now, the emergence of the tourism virtual community has broken this communication bottleneck and greatly increased the connection between tourists. The development of Internet technology is also bringing technical support for the development and improvement of the tourism virtual community. The tourism virtual community provides an important platform and channel for the dissemination of tourism information. More information comes

to users through the community. At the same time, the tourism virtual community has become a symbol of cultural trends.

Since the 21st century, the tourism virtual community has developed rapidly and become one of the hot spots of international tourism research. The tourism virtual community provides users with a new type of communication and interaction platform, which has changed the traditional communication mode of people and also derived interpersonal trust relationships in the network environment. In today's society, the Internet is the focus of online tourism. Tourism virtual communities benefit from the development of network technology, especially the popularity of mobile Internet.

The tourism virtual community brought by "Internet+tourism" is booming, and online tourism enterprises such as Ctrip, Tuniu, Feizhu, Tongcheng, and Mummy Donkey are establishing their own virtual communities. Now, with the strong atmosphere of the sharing economy, more tourism users are willing to share their travel itinerary and interesting stories in the virtual community. The virtual tourism community makes spatial geography no longer a problem. No matter how far apart, unfamiliar tourists can come together in the community through the network, opening the journey of mutual understanding and communication.

However, it also means that the first problem facing the virtual tourism community is trust. Generally speaking, members of the virtual community do not know much about the backgrounds of other members before they meet in the community. However, previous studies have shown that looking for peers is an important topic of interaction and communication among members of the tourism virtual community, second only to travel notes with pictures and texts, which indicates that one of the important functions of the tourism virtual community is to provide a platform for community members to look for travel companions in cyberspace. As of March 8, 2019, 394,666 virtual plans have been released in the virtual community of China's leading free travel service tourism website platform, attracting 623,080 users, and 1,306,806 users have signed up for the virtual plan. Joint travel is an organizational activity that requires trust to be realized, and the behavior of joint travel also indicates the establishment of a high degree of trust in the relationship. How does this high degree of trust relationship come into being when community users change from "strangers" who interact online to "small partners" who travel together? At present, there is no in-depth research on this new phenomenon in the academic community, so this paper hopes to find new value from this new phenomenon.

Trust is a relatively complex research topic that covers different disciplines in different fields. Researchers in each discipline have studied and discussed it from their own fields. These fields include sociology, economics, psychology, and computer science. Trust in real society is gradually generated by making use of kinship, geography, industry, and other relationships, but in virtual situations, these foundations do not exist. Network interpersonal trust is a perception and expectation formed among individuals in virtual situations. The application system in this situation is more open, and the degree of public accessibility is also higher. In addition, a highly dynamic service model accompanies it. These situational characteristics have brought many complex user relationships into virtual communities, including the abstract and difficult psychological cognition of network interpersonal trust.

The study found that users at both ends of the network can have interpersonal relationships in the virtual context because they have formed an atmosphere of social presence through understanding users' social clues and online communication. This atmosphere has narrowed the space and psychological distance between users at both ends of the network and then generated feelings and interpersonal relationships such as trust. In the tourism virtual community, trust relationship between users, specifically, how the social telepresence perception of each dimension affects the network interpersonal trust perception of each dimension, and the exploration of these problems will bring theoretical suggestions for the operation management and sustainable development of the community.

Since the late 1990s, scholars' research on trust in virtual communities has mainly focused on consumer trust in online shopping, but there are few studies on online interpersonal trust, especially from the perspective of social telepresence, to verify the internal relationship between social telepresence and online interpersonal trust in virtual communities through empirical methods. Therefore, this paper takes the tourism virtual community dedicated to finding fellow travelers as a research case. Through content analysis and online text analysis of user-generated content in the community, namely virtual travel posts, this paper conducts a questionnaire survey of users in the community and establishes a structural equation modeling (SEM) model. This paper explores the mechanism between social presence and online interpersonal trust in the tourism virtual community from the perspectives of trusted objects and trustors.

Online interaction is the core element of the virtual community. Members repeatedly participate in activities, often maintain close interaction, and establish strong emotional ties so as to form trust in each other in the virtual environment. The higher the level of interaction, the higher the degree of the user's virtual experience. The participation demand model of virtual community members built by Wang and Fesenmaier (2004) pointed out that the social demand for forming social relations with other members through building trust and forming connections was one of the basic needs for virtual members to participate in community interaction. Hoffman and Novak's (2018) research shows that online interaction can narrow the space and psychological distance between consumers and businesses at both ends of the network to create a sense of social presence similar to real interaction and promote the trust relationship between them. After 2008, with the development and growth of virtual tourism communities such as Virtual Tourist and Airbnb and the increase of online interaction in communities, researchers began to pay attention to the interactive behavior of tourism post writing and comments in communities. Lee and Gretzel (2014) pointed out that focusing on other consumers is one of the motivations of comment writers.

The above research shows that information sharing among community members can bring closer relationships to other community members to some extent, and information interaction is one of the important forms of online interaction. In 2011, HailinQu paid attention to the members of society. The interaction among members can adjust the influence of participation, identity, and contribution. As a process element, online interaction runs through the interaction between users at both ends of the network. Research shows that online interaction can effectively promote the trust relationship between consumers and online stores, which is much more influential than many explicit elements, especially in the maintenance and repair of trust (Chen & Chou, 2012).

Wang and Feng (2017) discussed the relationship between online interaction and brand trust. The results show that online interaction between members of virtual communities has a significant positive impact on brand trust. Online interaction can enable both parties to get more information about each other and get to know each other better, thus reducing the possible risks and uncertainties. Despite the reason, some scholars have explained it from the perspective of social interaction theory and social exchange theory. They believe that online interaction can send a signal to users, and users can affect their trust in the other side of the interaction through psychological processing and judgment of the signal. Based on this, online interaction is taken as an environmental factor to study social telepresence and online interpersonal trust. For members of the tourism virtual community, online interaction is the general environment and background for the formation of their social telepresence and online interpersonal trust, as well as a necessary condition that runs through the same process.

Relationship between social telepresence and network interpersonal trust

Because trust occurs in a social environment, social telepresence is a necessary condition for generating trust. An environment rich in social telepresence can stimulate trust perceptions among participants. Ye et al. (2020) successively proposed that social telepresence in virtual situations can also trigger trust. Skadberg (2004) regards presence as a feature of an immersive experience in web browsing.

Many scholars have confirmed that immersive experiences can stimulate consumers' trust perceptions. In terms of interpersonal trust, Cao et al. (2014) conducted a questionnaire survey on Sina Weibo users and applied regression analysis to demonstrate that social presence can positively affect the trust relationships of audiences. Shen and Khalifa (2008) divided social telepresence into three levels: conscious social telepresence, emotional social telepresence, and cognitive social telepresence. Through empirical research on the relationship between social telepresence and trust and stickiness, conscious social telepresence and cognitive social telepresence have significant positive effects on trust. Lu et al. (2016) found that the social presence factor based on social technology has a great impact on trust building in online exchange relationships and may also have an impact on consumers' purchase intentions. The research results of Gefen and Straub (2004) show that in order to gain the trust of consumers, the necessary condition is to build a high level of social presence. On the contrary, it is easier for websites to hide information and unreliable behaviors when the sense of social presence is low (Han et al., 2015). Therefore, trust can only develop under the conditions of a high level of social presence.

Similarly, a higher level of social telepresence will create more trust. Social telepresence theory believes that users have a psychological feeling of "person-to-person" communication in the process of interaction with the media, which is similar to real "face-to-face" communication with others; that is, users have an immersive social experience. Media with a high sense of social presence is likely to form good interactions between users, promote social emotions among users, and become the basis of network user communication. If you want to interact continuously in the virtual community, you can further develop interpersonal trust. In cyberspace, users with a strong sense of social telepresence can better experience intimate interpersonal relationships and can also generate stronger trust relationships. Based on this, the research makes the following assumptions:

H1: Consciousness of social presence positively affects network interpersonal trust.

H1a: Conscious social presence positively affects cognitive trust.

H1b: Conscious social presence positively affects emotional trust.

H2: Emotional social telepresence positively affects network interpersonal trust.

H2a: Emotional social presence positively affects cognitive trust.

H2b: Emotional social presence positively affects emotional trust.

H3: Cognitive social presence positively affects network interpersonal trust.

H3a: Cognitive social presence positively affects cognitive trust.

H3b: Cognitive social presence positively affects emotional trust.

Relationship between cognitive trust and emotional trust

McAllister (1995) believes that interpersonal trust can be divided into cognitive trust and emotional trust. Cognitive trust refers to the trustor's cognitive judgment on the ability and reliability of the trusted object by understanding the trusted object and predicting its ability to perform its duties through observation and other means. Emotional trust is based on emotion, and the trustor has confidence in the trusted object. The reason this trust can be generated is that the trustor feels that the trusted object cares about him, which is a kind of attitude foundation. In essence, this kind of trust is driven by emotion and certain emotional factors, which also leads to a relatively low level of clarity in the trustor's assessment of objective risks. In the field of psychology, cognition is emotion-oriented and also the source of emotion. Through literature, it has been found that there is also a close relationship between cognitive trust and emotional trust. Specifically, there may be a significant positive correlation between them.

In addition, cognitive trust may also have a guiding relationship with emotional trust. That is to say, if emotional trust is established between the trustor and the trusted object, there is not only a simple initial trust relationship between them but also a higher level of trust. The trust relationship has developed to a higher stage, which also means that an emotional bond is built between the trustor and the trusted

object. Therefore, suppose that there is a certain role between the two levels of network interpersonal trust, namely cognitive trust and emotional trust, and further speculate that cognitive trust plays a mediating role between social presence and emotional trust. Based on this, the research makes the following assumptions:

H4: Cognitive trust positively affects emotional trust.

H5: Cognitive trust plays a mediating role between social presence and emotional trust.

H5a: Cognitive trust plays a mediating role between conscious social presence and emotional trust.

H5b: Cognitive trust plays a mediating role between emotional social presence and emotional trust.

H5c: Cognitive trust plays a mediating role between cognitive social telepresence and emotional trust.

This paper studies the influencing factors of online interpersonal trust among users in the tourism virtual community from the perspective of social presence. Among them, social telepresence consists of three dimensions: conscious social telepresence, emotional social telepresence, and cognitive social telepresence. Network interpersonal trust consists of cognitive trust and emotional trust. Through empirical research, respectively, we verify the relationship between social telepresence and online interpersonal trust, the impact of three dimensions of social telepresence on online interpersonal trust, and the impact of three dimensions of social telepresence on two dimensions of online interpersonal trust. It aims to study the internal relationship and mechanisms comprehensively between social telepresence and online interpersonal trust.

Research Design

This study starts with the phenomenon of virtual travel and explores the mechanisms of online interpersonal trust formation in the virtual tourism community. This paper reviews the previous research progress on tourism virtual communities and network interpersonal trust through a literature review.

“Tourism virtual community,” “interpersonal trust,” “online interpersonal trust,” “virtual outing,” and other keywords that are searched on the largest Chinese academic databases from the Internet aside from Google Scholar are used as keywords to consult international literature review platforms such as the Science Citation Index. On the basis of careful reading, analysis, and summary of relevant literature, we have a clearer understanding of the current research status and process of tourism virtual communities and online interpersonal trust in academic circles at home and abroad. They also have an understanding of the current research gaps in this field, so as to select research objects with theoretical and practical significance, focus on the characteristics of virtual travel groups, the impact mechanism of social presence on online interpersonal trust, the overall model, and other contents.

Under the joint guidance of social presence, social identity, symbolic interaction, social exchange, and commitment trust theories (Shen et al., 2010), it is planned to conduct this investigation by combining qualitative and quantitative research methods. Network interpersonal trust exists in a dual structure. Previous studies have investigated the trustor’s level of trust in the trusted object from the perspective of the trustor rather than the trustee’s credibility. This research intends to study the formation mechanism of online interpersonal trust in the tourism virtual community from the perspectives of trusted objects and trustors, determine the basic characteristics of trusted objects and investigate their credibility using content analysis and text analysis, and collect relevant data using a questionnaire survey under the guidance of social telepresence theory. This paper analyzes the social telepresence perception level and network interpersonal trust perception level of users in virtual communities, uses a structural equation model to verify the internal relationship between social telepresence and network interpersonal trust, which is the research focus of this paper, and obtains the mechanism between them, thus providing a theoretical basis for the development of tourism virtual communities.

Qualitative research on network interpersonal trust mainly focuses on trust crisis research and the analysis of trust-related phenomena. The content is relatively short on specific social context and application significance. Therefore, in this study, the formation process of network interpersonal trust is studied through online tourism activities organized by virtual travel groups, which are based on specific phenomena and have a certain social context. This research adopts a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods. Virtual travel can be more deeply analyzed, while the characteristics of this group can also show the enlightenment behind the phenomenon and the dynamic process of the formation of interpersonal trust on the Internet. In addition, social presence and interpersonal trust on the Internet are both complex concepts, and the internal relationship between them cannot be fully studied through a single research method. Therefore, this paper selects a research method that combines qualitative and quantitative methods and uses content analysis and online text analysis. To investigate the credibility of the trusted objects, use the questionnaire method to measure the social presence and interpersonal trust perception of community users, and use the SEM structural equation to verify the internal relationship between the two.

Most of the research on interpersonal trust on the Internet directly focuses on the vast number of Internet users. There is little research on specific tourism virtual communities. Based on this, this paper selects the virtual community of the tourism network as the research case. The tourism website is a new free travel service platform based on tourism social networking and tourism big data. It is widely concerned and loved by domestic and foreign tourism enthusiasts and is known as 'China's travel bible.' By systematically integrating various user experiences such as community atmosphere, travel culture, product functions, social interaction, travel decision-making, and transactions, stable user traffic is obtained. Users generate content through participation and interaction on the platform. These UGCs form structured data streams through data mining and analysis and circulate on the Internet. Relying on social gene, UGC (user-generated content), tourism big data, and free trade platforms become the three core competitiveness factors, and social gene is the essential feature different from other online tourism websites.

Since 2006, community users have spontaneously set up a virtual travel group on the platform, where tourists from all over the world gather to travel together. In order to encourage users to share and interact, encourage users to travel, find their peers, and launch a series of measures, including its characteristic virtual community, This virtual community aims to enable users to find like-minded strangers by publishing information and travel needs, and to embark on the journey together. Therefore, this study selects the virtual plan posts in the community for online text analysis and issues questionnaires among members of the community for empirical research. From the perspective of trusted objects and trustors, this study comprehensively and stereoscopically studies the construction of interpersonal trust relationships in the network.

Research on Network Interpersonal Trust from the Perspective of Trusted Objects

Network interpersonal trust is a concept from a dual perspective, including the two important roles of trustor and trusted object. Through previous scholars' research literature, it has been found that the current research on network interpersonal trust mainly focuses on the trust perception level of trustors (Hardin, 2002). However, trust is a concept of a dual structure of "trustors and trusted objects," which is equally important for the study of trusted objects. Therefore, it is necessary to pay direct attention to the trusteeship and its influencing factors. In tourism virtual communities, trusted objects refer to users who actively publish information and organize tourism activities in the community, namely "virtual event organizers," and trustors refer to users who receive information, that is, "virtual activity participants." The personal information and image display of the trusted object exposed on the personal homepage are the source of the trust relationship and also an important measure to establish a sense of social presence. The aims are to take the virtual community as an example, take 525 users as samples, study their information characteristics as trusted objects, analyze the basic characteristics and credibility of "virtual activity

participants”, compare the characteristics of different objects with high trust and low trust, and explore the construction of network interpersonal trust relationships.

Source and Processing of Sample Data

Since the development of the tourism virtual community, it has derived a variety of types, including the tourism sector set up by the virtual community, such as Douban and Tianya communities, which mainly meet the community users’ demand for tourism activities; user review and communication communities set up under comprehensive websites, such as Ctrip, Tongcheng Travel, and Qunar.com, which are mainly aimed at attracting tourism consumption, taking the community as a communication platform for consumers, and triggering a new round of consumption behavior; and an open platform for travel journal sharing. For example, such communities focus on interaction between UGC (user-generated content) and users.

Network interpersonal trust is based on social relations, and social genes are the essential characteristics different from other online travel websites. Relying on UGC (user-generated content), tourism big data, and free trade platforms, it has three core competitiveness. Users generate content through participation and interaction on the platform. These UGCs form structured data streams through data mining and analysis and circulate on the Internet. To encourage users to share and interact, we launched the characteristic virtual community. This virtual community aims to enable users to find like-minded strangers by publishing information and travel needs, and to embark on the journey together. This trust realization of online interaction results requires great changes in interpersonal trust between the two sides and can also better reflect the formation process of online interpersonal trust. Therefore, this research selects users who organize virtual travel activities online in the virtual community as the research samples of trusted objects, analyzes the portrait characteristics of users, and conducts online text analysis on virtual plan posts to study the construction of network interpersonal trust relationships from the perspective of trusted objects.

Sample Data Capture

The virtual plan post is the information display of the trusted objects in the tourism virtual community, represents the commitment to the trustor, and belongs to the online user-generated content. Its main content includes a text description of the user’s tourism activities and personal and scenic photos of the tourism destination. Based on the research ideas and framework of this paper, when grabbing the virtual post, only the text content is downloaded and sorted, and the content outside the text is not grabbed. Since expired or ended posts will be taken off the shelf in the platform, this article will no longer capture posts that have been taken off the shelf before the time. For posts that have not expired yet, considering that virtual activities are related to the time of posting, the longer the time is, the more attention and further interaction may be received. Therefore, this article only captures the posts that will expire on the same day when capturing data. In addition, considering the schedule of paper writing, this study only focuses on the virtual plan posts from March 1 to May 31, 2021. The capture period coincides with the May Day holiday, so residents have more travel needs and more virtual posts, which is conducive to expanding the representativeness and universality of the sample.

As users initiating virtual activities in the tourism virtual community, the sample objects are independent individuals in the virtual environment. Their personal images, in addition to virtual posts, also include basic personal information, image characteristics in the community, and records of past tourism activities. This article takes virtual posts as the starting point, continues to capture various kinds of information exposed by sample users in the community, and collates them to obtain complete user information, which will be used as a tool to create a sense of social presence and judge the interpersonal trust relationship on the network.

The design steps of this chapter are as follows: on the basis of determining the selection of sample sources, pre-collect the samples to determine the scientificity of the collection method, and then establish subsequent collection rules to conduct formal collection under the guidance of the rules. After the completion of sample collection, this research will conduct content analysis on the sample data so as to obtain the basic characteristics of the trusted objects, conduct high-frequency statistics and analysis on the samples, and use software to build social network relationships. On this basis, the data will be deeply evaluated and interpreted. In terms of effective sample screening, through pre-collection, the following principles were established: (1) virtual posts in forms other than photography and other words were excluded; (2) virtual posts irrelevant to tourism; (3) virtual posts such as advertising and marketing; (4) repeated virtual posts published by the same author and content many times; and (5) meaningless virtual post replies.

During the collection process, it was found that some comments under the posts were irrelevant to the content of the posts and suspected of marketing and advertising. These comments have been deleted. In the process of data capture, due to the large number of virtual posts, it is difficult to read and collect all the posts in the virtual community. Therefore, on the basis of establishing the above screening principles, the first post on March 1, 2021, will be used as the starting collection point, and every three posts will be identified manually. If the posts belong to the screening principles, they will be postponed to the next post for reevaluation. The last virtual post until May 31, 2021, serves as the final collection point to ensure the continuity, universality, and representativeness of the sample distribution. Among them, different research methods are used in the research process at different stages. First of all, the basic characteristics of the users of the virtual community partnering activities (e.g., gender, city, degree of activity) and the selection of virtual tourism activities (e.g., organization form, city popularity), using content analysis methods and manual identification operations, finally obtained the basic characteristics of virtual activity organizers and virtual activities in the virtual tourism community. Secondly, we use ROSTCM6 software to do word segmentation and word frequency statistics for virtual post text and use relevant mathematical analysis methods to study its importance. On this basis, high-frequency word analysis is conducted to draw out the information disclosure characteristics of virtual event organizers for the construction of trust relationships. Third, we use the software to build the semantic network of tourism event organizers, explore the semantic relationship of keywords, and analyze the virtual post feature network.

Sorting of Sample Data

Through the above sample data capture method, 525 users were obtained as research samples for this paper. The information captured by each user includes the following aspects: (1) The content that the community platform requires users to fill in when registering accounts, such as nickname, gender, and residence, cannot guarantee the absolute authenticity of such information in a virtual environment, but when the sample size is sufficient, individual false information can be ignored, determine that such information is true; (2) The identity characteristics given by the platform to users, such as the membership level and the amount of money, can be rewarded by the platform by participating in community activities, interacting with other users and other behaviors, so as to improve the level and increase the amount of money that can be used as transaction currency. This part of the content shows how active users are in the community; (3) Social information of users in the community, including their attention, fans, published travel notes, number of replies and readings obtained from travel notes, questions and answers they participated in, comments they participated in, and virtual activities they participated in, records the track of users' online participation in interaction in the past; (4) Information related to launching virtual activities, including virtual posts, departure time, travel days, departure place, destination, and travel number requirements, is the entry point to attract other users to pay attention to virtual activities; (5) Interactive information of virtual posts, including the number of visitors and applicants, the number of men and women who have signed up, the number of people who have followed, and the message of posts, reflects the response of virtual activities, and is also an important basis for measuring the interpersonal trust relationship in the network. In the Excel

table, each user is regarded as a serial number corresponding to relevant information and text expressions, which is regarded as a complete information bar for subsequent processing.

Statistics show that after manual identification and screening, the total number of virtual plan posts is 525, each with a different length and content style, and the text is sorted on the basis of statistics. First, delete and replace the unconventional characters in the text, including common network symbols and meaningless punctuation marks. Secondly, in the process of manual recognition and capture, we should change and replace the wrong characters in the text without changing the meaning of the text to ensure the overall quality of the text. Finally, Microsoft Word processing software is used to adjust the overall format and layout of the text and convert it into a “.txt” format file for the next step of Chinese text segmentation and content analysis. After deletion, selection, and replacement, the final text has a total of 140,000 words and an average of 267 words.

Sample Data Processing

On the basis of data sorting, the Chinese text content is cleaned and processed, including word segmentation, undefined word recognition, part of speech tagging, and other steps. First, import the sorted text document into the ROSTCM6 software and use the software to automatically segment words. On the basis of the software segmentation results, the wrong word segmentation content is corrected, and the correct word segmentation words are added to the user's dictionary. For example, "Everest," “base camp,” "personality,” and “cheerful” in the software word segmentation results actually refer to “Everest base camp” and “cheerful personality” in the context of specific proper nouns.

Therefore, after adding new word segmentation words, adjust and modify the word segmentation results of each document to ensure that the subsequent word frequency and semantic analysis do not have word segmentation deviation, so that the output results are consistent with the actual situation. At the same time, filter words that have unclear references, no significant meaning, and have nothing to do with this research, such as “can” and "one." Finally, synonymous replacement is conducted for words with similar meanings and different words to avoid deviation caused by word frequency separation.

Except for the virtual plan post-text, other information is processed by mathematical statistics analysis and content analysis. Manual identification is conducted through Excel tables, and further analysis is conducted on this basis. For information that may be false, such as gender and city of residence, judge the true situation by combining the information filled in by the user with the relevant information revealed in other information on the homepage, screen and modify the false information, and then conduct subsequent analysis.

Credibility Analysis of Trusted Objects

The current research on network interpersonal trust is mainly to investigate the trust perception level of the trustor (Hardin, 2002). Later, scholars paid attention to the trusted objects and found that trustors were largely affected by social identity information and other factors in the process of credibility evaluation of trusted objects (Brewer, 2008; Kramer, 1999; Lount, 2010; Maddux & Brewer, 2005, as cited by Xin & Xin, 2014). Generally speaking, the more trusted objects reveal their multiple social identities, the more they can gain trust. This paper will start with the characteristics of the trusted objects and examine their trustworthiness level, specifically their reputation with network organizations, offline activities of network organizations, and their interaction experience with network organizations and familiarity. This paper mainly analyzes the reputation of online visible network organizations and their interaction experience and familiarity.

Basic Characteristics of Trusted Objects Based on Mathematical Statistics

The virtual community is a platform for publishing virtual information and organizing online tourism activities. The companion community users and other virtual community users have more pure tourism characteristics. Analyzing the demographic characteristics, grades, travel days, travel organization methods, and travel destination choices of the trusted objects (virtual event organizers), is helpful to understand the characteristics of virtual users in depth.

Gender and city distribution of trusted objects

The virtual community platform requires users to fill in gender information when registering and logging in. After clicking to enter their personal home page, a gender tag will be displayed next to their nickname to show that they are male or female. However, the website does not make a mandatory requirement, so users can choose not to fill in gender. In addition to the gender label, there will also be text representations that show their gender in the text, and the gender will be judged through the representations. Through the combination of the two aspects, it is found that 525 users in the trusted object sample include 251 male users and 209 female users, and the gender of 65 users can neither be queried from the website information nor judged from the text. This paper gives a null value for the gender of these users. In general, the proportion of male users is slightly higher than that of female users, with male users accounting for 47.8% and female users accounting for 39.8%. 12.4% of users have not exposed their gender. It shows that men are more willing than women to seek virtual travel in the tourism virtual community, while women's offices may have a weak demand for virtual travel for personal safety reasons. With regard to the source of residence of the survey sample users, except for 97 users who have not indicated their cities, it is found through the collation of the user's residence information that users come from all over the country and 13 users live abroad. Specifically, it includes the United States, Copenhagen (Denmark), Paris (France), Adelaide (Australia), the Netherlands, Cape Town (South Africa), Gwangju (South Korea), Seoul (South Korea), Morocco, and Singapore. The top ten cities with the largest number of users include: Chengdu (including Shudu) with 52 users; Beijing (including Didu, Haidian District, and Chaoyang District) with 47 users; Shanghai (including Mordor) with 28 users; Shenzhen with 27 users; Guangzhou with 25 users; Chongqing (including Chengdu) with 16 users; Suzhou and Hangzhou with nine users each; and Nanjing and Hulun Buir with six users each.

People in Chengdu, the "leisure city," live a leisurely life, as they love to play and have time and energy to conduct tourism activities. On the other hand, Chengdu is now a place where young people live. The younger generation prefers to use the Internet to conduct travel activities through virtual space. As China's first-tier cities, Beijing, Shanghai, Shenzhen, and Guangzhou have a high level of economic development, a high quality of life, and a greater demand for tourism. At the same time, they also have the economic strength to travel. Suzhou and Hangzhou, which enjoy the reputation of "paradise on earth and Suzhou and Hangzhou on earth," are also cities with many virtual community users. These two cities in the south of Chang Jiang are rich in tourism atmosphere and are representatives of Jiangnan tourism destinations in China. People living in these two cities will also have a strong desire to travel and launch travel activities in the tourism virtual community due to the influence of the tourism atmosphere.

In general, most users of virtual communities come from cities with relatively high economic development levels. These people have sufficient economic capacity, controllable time, money, and leisure. Through subsequent research, it was found that this has a lot to do with the age level of users, which will be further proved in the future. From the registration of virtual posts, a total of 1,297 users signed up for 525 virtual activities. The average number of people signing up for each activity was 2.47. 129 travel activities failed to be virtually successful. 319 activities were signed up for one to five people. 77 activities were signed up for more than six people. The maximum number of people signing up was 11. The probability of virtual success in the virtual community is 75.43%. In addition, users who sign up for virtual activities play the role of trustors in this research. The gender distribution of trustors can also be obtained through the activity page. According to the statistics of 525 virtual posts, 1,288 male applicants and 730

female applicants, respectively, account for 63.8% and 36.2% of the total number of applicants. On average, in 525 activities, the average number of applicants for each activity was 2.45 for men and 1.39 for women, or 1.76 times that of women. The difference between male and female sex ratios was obvious. This also shows that male users are more likely than female users to participate in tourism activities in the virtual environment. This paper will prove this point in the subsequent empirical research. Under the virtual posts, nearly half of the posts have no replies at all.

High-frequency word analysis

Scholars generally believe that the more frequently a word is used in expression, the higher the recognition of the group of speakers. When applied to the research on the social clues and credibility of the trusted objects, that is, the trusted objects pay more attention to the elements mentioned more times, which reflects that the trusted objects think that the elements can arouse the trust of others. Therefore, in this study, ROSTCM6 analysis software is used to conduct a statistical analysis of the high word frequency of the virtual posts of the publishers of virtual travel activities or trusted objects. The specific operation process is as follows:

- ① Set the cleaned and processed virtual post text as a plain text document;
- ② Use the word segmentation function of ROSTCM6 software to divide all sentences into completely independent words.
- ③ Check the word segmentation results, replace synonyms of words with similar meanings but different words, avoid deviation caused by frequent word separation, and correct the wrong word segmentation results and some meaningful but not correct word segmentation contents. Add the correct word segmentation words to the user's dictionary, such as distinguishing "Qinghai" from "Qinghai Lake," "Princess Disease," "Everest Headquarters," "Qinghai Tibet Railway," "carpooling," and other words with practical significance in special situations, and words with repetitive meanings are merged (e.g., girl, sister);
- ④ After word segmentation, add a filtered word list to filter words with unclear references, no significant meaning, and irrelevant to this research, such as "then," "this time," and "probably," and filter function words such as "ah" and "ba."
- ⑤ The "word frequency analysis" function of the software is used to derive the top 120 high-frequency words with the highest frequency, which are listed in descending order in the high-frequency word list. The travel position is the first, which is determined by the industry and object of study. For virtual travel event organizers, the recipients of virtual posts are users who may participate in virtual travel activities, and the travel schedule is the most important information for travel. With the interpretation in the virtual post-expression environment, the high-frequency words that can reflect the information of virtual activity combinators are classified and refined. The main operation process is as follows: first, the high-frequency characteristic words in the high-frequency vocabulary of the travel notes are abstracted, and the high-frequency words index categories of six dimensions, namely, manual identification and judgment of travel arrangements, tourism destination selection, travel needs, virtual purposes, and partnering requirements, are used. The information disclosure content of virtual event organizers is relatively scattered, and there is no particularly obvious node. However, itinerary and departure are more important nodes for virtual tour organizers to disclose information.

From this semantic network diagram, we can draw the following obvious conclusions: in the information disclosure of virtual event organizers, the disclosure of travel arrangements is the main part, and the key elements such as distance, time, and collection are the important focus of virtual activities; The presentation of tourist destinations also accounts for a large part, especially in the northwest cities such as Dunhuang, Zhangye, and Xining, which is consistent with the analysis of high-frequency words, which

shows that users in virtual communities tend to choose destinations. From the perspective of the number of years that respondents have used the Internet, 86.55% of the population has more than five years of Internet age, of which the largest proportion is users with more than nine years of Internet age; In terms of the number of years that respondents have used the virtual community, 81 respondents have more than five years of experience, accounting for 13.97% of the total sample. It can be seen that the virtual community is still a relatively new online community. In addition, 76.55% of respondents have used the virtual community for 1–5 years. This shows that most of the respondents have a certain number of years of service and have a certain understanding of the virtual community. From the average time users spend using the virtual community every day, users spend 0.5–4 hours on the virtual community every day, which shows that they have a deep understanding of the community and have a certain degree of dependence. In general, the number of respondents who chose the shorter or longer time options of less than 0.5 hours and more than 4 hours was relatively small, and the number of respondents who chose other time periods was relatively evenly distributed. Specifically, 35.69% of the respondents used 1-2 hours a day. From the frequency of respondents using "virtual" communities, 167 respondents log in to the community every day, accounting for 28.79% in total, of which 14.31% log in more than once a day, 14.48% log in once a day, and the frequency of other users participating in the survey is not too high. As a tool that is not used daily, virtual communities are used less frequently than WeChat, QQ, microblogs, and other social platforms.

Conclusion

In the network environment, interpersonal trust relationships are affected by many factors, and the research on the influencing factors of interpersonal trust relationships has increasingly practical significance, especially for the tourism field, where trust is an important proposition. Based on the perspective of social telepresence, this paper applies structural equations to construct a theoretical model of the role of social telepresence in the network interpersonal trust relationship in the tourism virtual community and puts forward the research hypothesis of this paper.

Taking the virtual community as an example, this paper analyzes the credibility of the virtual event organizer, namely, the trusted object, and conducts a questionnaire survey of the virtual event participants, namely, the trusted persons. In order to ensure that the measurement scales involved in the research can be applied to the research objects and research situations, some projects have been adjusted and modified according to the needs of the research issues on the basis of reference to the mature scales at home and abroad. In order to further ensure the feasibility of the scale, after collecting the data, the reliability and validity of the required data were evaluated. After that, the basic assumptions of this paper were verified. Through hypothesis testing, it was found that hypothesis 3 (including hypotheses 3a and 3b), hypothesis 4, and hypothesis 5c have passed the significance test, and the hypothesis is valid.

The mechanism of network interpersonal trust is becoming more important in the tourism virtual community. This paper explores the mechanism of network interpersonal trust among users of the tourism virtual community from the perspective of social presence. The concept of social telepresence is mainly used to describe interpersonal communication, interaction, and other activities. This kind of perception indicates that individuals in the network situation, in the process of interacting with others, have a sense of the immediate presence of other individuals. Social telepresence also includes the perception of intimacy between other individuals. The results of this study show that social telepresence can positively affect the trust relationship of the audience, and cognitive social telepresence has a more significant impact on the trust relationship.

Network interpersonal trust is divided into two levels: “cognitive trust” and “emotional trust.” The data validation results show that cognitive trust has a significant positive impact on the formation of emotional trust, and cognitive trust plays a mediating role between cognitive social presence and emotional trust. Therefore, this paper conducts mining reasoning through the formation mechanism of network

interpersonal trust in the tourism virtual community, presents the trust relationship between users of the tourism virtual community, enables the management platform of the tourism virtual community to mine valuable potential trust chain information, and enables the platform to make better choices in the trust chain, which is of great significance for guiding the construction of a more trusted and harmonious tourism virtual community.

Trust is a kind of psychological state. In the network environment, when two parties interact online and one party at both ends of the network has confidence in the trust, ability, and integrity of the other party, they will perceive interpersonal trust in the network, making the two parties have close relationships and becoming an important way to build and maintain relationships. At the same time, interpersonal trust helps to strengthen users' cognition of information in interaction, reduce the cost of identifying information and obtaining real information, and further improve users' acceptance of interaction. The results of this study show that the formation of online interpersonal trust is conducive to the formation of users' willingness to continue to participate and is conducive to further promoting mutual interaction.

References

- Brewer, M. B. (2008). Depersonalized trust and ingroup cooperation. In J. I. Krueger (Ed.), *Rationality and social responsibility* (pp. 215-232). Psychology Press.
<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203889695-10/depersonalized-trust-ingroup-cooperation-marilynn-brewer>
- Cao, J., Wu, J., Shi, W., Liu, B., Zheng, X., & Luo, J. (2014). Sina microblog information diffusion analysis and prediction. *Chinese Journal of Computers*, 37(4), 779-790.
<http://cjc.ict.ac.cn/online/onlinepaper/cjx-2014415113515.pdf>
- Chen, Y. T., & Chou, T. Y. (2012). Exploring the continuance intentions of consumers for B2C online shopping: Perspectives of fairness and trust. *Online Information Review*, 36(1), 104-125.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/14684521211209572>
- Gefen, D., & Straub, D. W. (2004). Consumer trust in B2C e-Commerce and the importance of social presence: experiments in e-Products and e-Services. *Omega*, 32(6), 407-424.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2004.01.006>
- Han, S., Min, J., & Lee, H. (2015). Antecedents of social presence and gratification of social connection needs in SNS: A study of Twitter users and their mobile and non-mobile usage. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(4), 459-471.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2015.04.004>
- Hardin, R. (2002). *Trust and trustworthiness*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Hoffman, D. L., & Novak, T. P. (2018). Consumer and object experience in the internet of things: An assemblage theory approach. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 44(6), 1178-1204.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucx105>
- Kramer, R. M. (1999). Trust and distrust in organizations: Emerging perspectives, enduring questions. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 50(1), 569-598. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.50.1.569>
- Lee, Y. J., & Gretzel, U. (2014). Cross-cultural differences in social identity formation through travel blogging. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 31(1), 37-54.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2014.861701>
- Lount, R. B., Jr. (2010). The impact of positive mood on trust in interpersonal and intergroup interactions. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 98(3), 420-433.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2010-02829-006>
- Lu, B., Fan, W., & Zhou, M. (2016). Social presence, trust, and social commerce purchase intention: An empirical research. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 56, 225-237.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.11.057>

- Maddux, W. W., & Brewer, M. B. (2005). Gender differences in the relational and collective bases for trust. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 8(2), 159-171. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430205051065>
- McAllister, D. J. (1995). Affect-and cognition-based trust as foundations for interpersonal cooperation in organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(1), 24-59. <https://doi.org/10.5465/256727>
- Shen, K. N., & Khalifa, M. (2008). Exploring multidimensional conceptualization of social presence in the context of online communities. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 24(7), 722-748. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447310802335789>
- Shen, K. N., Yu, A. Y., & Khalifa, M. (2010). Knowledge contribution in virtual communities: accounting for multiple dimensions of social presence through social identity. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 29(4), 337-348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290903156622>
- Skadberg, Y. X., Skadberg, A. N., & Kimmel, J. R. (2004). Flow experience and its impact on the effectiveness of a tourism website. *Information Technology & Tourism*, 7(3-4), 147-156. <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/cog/itt/2004/00000007/F0020003/art00002>
- Wang, X., & Feng, W. (2017). The influence of social interaction and para-social interaction in virtual brand community on brand relationship quality. *Collected Essays on Finance and Economics*, 220(5), 78-88. <http://cjlc.zufe.edu.cn/CN/Y2017/V220/I5/78>
- Wang, Y., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2004). Modeling participation in an online travel community. *Journal of Travel Research*, 42(3), 261-270. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287503258824>
- Xin, Z., & Xin, S. (2014). The influence of trustees' social identity complexity on their trustworthiness. *Acta Psychologica Sinica*, 46(3), 415-426. <https://journal.psych.ac.cn/xlxb/CN/10.3724/SP.J.1041.2014.00415>
- Ye, S., Lei, S. I., Shen, H., & Xiao, H. (2020). Social presence, telepresence and customers' intention to purchase online peer-to-peer accommodation: A mediating model. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 42, 119-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2019.11.008>